

ISic3359

Ash chest for Gaius Matrinius Felikion

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

ash chest

Editor

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Autopsy

2006.07.25; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Hypogeum in Grotticelli, excavated 4 July 1902

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 22226

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 25.5 cm

Width 43.5 cm

Depth 37.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 35-60 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Γ(αι) · Ματρίνι

2. Φηλικίων ·

3. χρη(στὲ) · καὶ · ἄμε(μπτε) · χαῖρε

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Gaius Matrinius Felikion, worthy and blameless, farewell!

Commentary

Φηλικίων presumably renders the Latin Felicianus. Although the inscription is in Greek, it is noteworthy that it employs a Latin vocative form for Matrinius (implicit therefore also for Gaius), as well as abbreviating the formulaic words χρηστὲ and ἄμεμπτε, according to the more normal practices of Latin inscriptions. Ferrua suggests that the letters are of the third century AD, but an earlier date also seems possible

Digital identifiers:

TM 644864

Bibliography

Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 217 no.97

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014